

////////////////////////////////////
**BEYOND TECHCARDS: A FIRST STEP TOWARD THE
INVESTIGATION OF NEW DIMENSIONS OF INTERMEDIATE
REPRESENTATIONS TO SUPPORT THE CREATIVE PROCESS
OF EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES**
////////////////////////////////////

Ioana Ocnarescu* Florentin Rodio* Alexis Eve* Jean-Baptiste Labrune*
Carole Bouchard** Améziane Aoussat**

* Alcatel-Lucent Bell Labs France, ioana_cristina.ocnarescu@alcatel-lucent.com

** LCPI Arts et Métiers ParisTech France, carole.bouchard@paris.ensam.fr

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a design tool that supports collaboration, communication and creativity in a context of highly specialized technological complexity and within a multidisciplinary team. This study analyses the impact of such intermediate tools, the TechCards, by exploring two research questions. The first investigates the effect of the tool in a creativity session. The second examines the opportunity to turn a typical creativity session into a gaming experience with the TechCards. Creativity production and intrinsic motivation were measured. Results showed that our intermediate objects improve fluency and adaptation of ideation related to our industrial context; plus, the game condition combined with TechCards enhances intrinsic motivation and the overall creativity of the generated ideas. The implications of these findings and future research tracks are discussed.

Keywords: Design tool, Intermediate representations, Creativity, Serious gaming, Intrinsic motivation.

INTRODUCTION

In modern technological research companies, designers and human-centered researchers work with technical specialists to understand, apprehend and interact with technology in order to find innovative user-centered applications.

In a context of technological complexity and highly specialized technical knowledge, the challenge for a design team is to create tools and methods to understand technology and support the design process in more efficient, engaging and playful ways. Moreover the designer is sometimes confronted to develop additional tools to improve the

communication and the collaboration within a multidisciplinary team, and thus invents new ways to share, discuss and create ideas. Mer et al. (1995) presents the role of such tools that they call intermediate objects.

INTERMEDIATE OBJECTS: A LEARNING AND COMMUNICATIONAL TOOL IN THE DESIGN PROCESS

Intermediate objects in research

There are different names used in the literature to define such support-materials: intermediate models in design research, external or shared representations in psychology, and artifacts in software development process. However the concept of intermediate objects comes from social sciences like ethnography and sociology. Vinck (2009) observes a tendency towards materialization of the methods and of the tools in these fields for a better order, structure and coordination. He also discusses how in scientific cooperation networks, these intermediate objects (instruments, texts, representations) are used to better understand scientific facts and to support discussions in the research community (Vinck, 1999).

In design science, depending on the phase of design process, these objects could be a material for presentation, identification and translation for technologies, ideas, models (Vinck, 2009) and therefore a great tool for coordination and communication. Another property of intermediate objects is the fact that they could be close or open (Vinck, 2009), depending of their use in the process. Open objects encourage the divergence and the interpretation and they could be used as inspirational material. The close objects are used to inform, to present or to prescript a task or other specifications.

Bouchard, Camous, and Aoussat (2005) present a case study where intermediate representations were created and used to introduce two aspects in the design process: a communication between the persons involved in the creativity session and a tool that stimulated the collective creativity. According to these authors, “cards have a playful effect, recognized for its efficiency during creative sessions involving sometimes conflictual debates between different corporations... The use of visual matter, such as illustrations and photographs, and of simple keywords, answered the need for very simple representations” (Bouchard et al., 2005, p.17).

Another tool created to improve collaborative work in multidisciplinary teams is presented by Moggridge (2006). He describes how IDEO design team produced a method based on cards to encourage and support a creative approach for the design team. This method groups 51 cards. Each card contains a textual description of a method, a brief example of its use and “an illustrative and sometimes whimsical image on the other side” (Moggridge, 2006, p.669). This tool was created for designers and has two roles depending on the purpose of the project. The first one, a generative one, was created for designing new ideas in a specific domain of activity. The second one, an evaluative one, tests the potential of a design solution for a better redefinition. Finally, having a paper support, these cards “... can be used flexibly to sort, browse, search, spread out, or pin up” (Moggridge, 2006, p.669).

Nevertheless all these intermediate tools are not chosen arbitrary. Vinck (1999) argues that these tools have a big impact on the research process. Both the creation of this material and the use these intermediate objects, influence the way teams collaborate and share a common understanding. Besides, a multidisciplinary team is composed both of “visualizers” like designers and of “low imagers” or “verbalizers” (Vinck, 1999). The choice of the inspirational support changes depending on the actors’ role in the design process. Moreover even if this support is created for a particular purpose, sometimes secondary roles are discovered during its use and interaction.

The TechCards

In a previous study, we tested the concept of intermediate objects and we created a visual and tangible tool that optimizes the communication between the members of multidisciplinary teams, named TechCards (Ocnarescu, Bouchard, Aoussat, Pain, & Sciamma, 2011). These technological cards are easy-to-understand representations of technologies developed in our research center. They were created to help designers, technical and human specialists to share a common knowledge of technology. They are plastic A5 cards, made of 8 parts (see Figure 1): title of the technology, an image, a short textual description, technical characteristics, research questions, the contact of the creator of the technology and two indicators, ownership and maturity level.

Figure 1. A TechCard composition on both sides:

- | | |
|--|--------------------------------|
| 1 - Technology name, | 5 - Ownership, |
| 2 - Metaphorical image, | 6 - Technical characteristics, |
| 3 - Short description of the technology, | 7 - What to improve points, |
| 4 - Maturity level, | 8 - Location & contact. |

These cards were created and used in the first phase of our design process in order to understand the technological blocks that were a key to the project. Furthermore, we used this material in creativity sessions in order to see its influence in the creative process. These preliminary studies showed that we could consider the TechCards as a bridge that connected the design team and the technical specialists. The pleasant aspect of the TechCards, their tangibility and playful aspect and the image that represented their technology had a motivational effect in the working process. Depending on the

actors involved in this project, the TechCards had a different roles, impact and usage. For the technical specialists, this constraint format helped them to visualize, materialize and make tangible pure technological thoughts, ideas and algorithms. Each card that was a proof of their work and having this material that present their effort made them proud (Ocnarescu et al., 2011). For the team leaders of the project, this intermediate material created a global overview over the resources deployed in this process and helped them to better organize the deadline of the project. For the designers and human science specialists, due to the high specificity of the context, the TechCards were a necessity. Moreover the observations gathered during our creativity sessions with these cards, made us believe that the TechCards could be an inspirational tool in the creative process (Ocnarescu et al., 2011). These first results conducted us to continue our studies and test the motivational and creative potential of the TechCards.

INTERMEDIATE OBJECTS IN SERIOUS GAMING SESSION

Definition & mechanisms

What is a serious game? Usually, a serious game is defined as a program having a serious purpose, such as marketing, education, health or training, based on playful elements derived from video games (Alvarez, 2007). Using several motivational leverages based on human psychology, such as Flow (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990), Self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000) or Captology (Fogg, 2003), serious games are the perfect candidate to enhance a large spectrum of activities. By increasing the deliberate selection, persistence and likelihood of repetitive usages of a specific activity (Oerter, 1999), different works have already showed the potential of serious gaming on learning, development and social change (Ritterfeld, Cody, & Vorderer, 2009).

However, the source of enjoyment depends heavily on the users' preferences. For instance, the Demographic Game Design (DGD) describes four player types and their associated game play-preferences (Bateman & Boon, 2005):

- the Conqueror, driven by competition and domination;

- the Manager, driven by intellectual and skill mastery;
- the Wanderer, driven by new and easy-fun experience;
- the Participant, driven by social interaction.

Thus, different types of games coexist to satisfy different players. However, to design a game enjoyable for a maximum of users, one should define carefully its elements of play, in order to take into account these different profiles. As a result, the design of a serious game should be supported by a deep knowledge of players and game mechanisms consistent with the activity.

Serious games in creativity

Why using serious games in creativity? At least for three reasons: to create a favorable creative climate, to motivate participants, and to act directly on the ideation process.

Firstly, games create a special space, separated from the real and ordinary life, both spatially and temporally (Huizinga, 1971). Thus, by facilitating the creation of an informal atmosphere, games reduce the effects of common social influences on idea generation, such as social loafing or production blocking (Triantafyllakos, Palaigeorgiou, & Tsoukalas, 2011). In addition, the playing session, bounded by rules, provide a solid facilitator for the idea generation session, by making it progress in an orderly fashion and providing an equal chance for all (Kultima, Niemelä, Paavilainen, & Saarenpää, 2010).

Secondly, games can boost significantly the internal motivation of participants, which is a very important requirement, or even, a sine qua non condition in creative production (Amabile, 1996). Among all motivational leverage coming from games, competition, *Agon* (Caillois, 1957) is the most used. This challenge increases the motivation in of participants, especially when the group is composed exclusively of men (Conti, Collins, & Picariello, 2001). Furthermore, a game only fulfills its purpose if the outcome of the activity is unforeseeable. This is why games must contain a sufficient portion of unpredictability for the player, by adding randomness elements, *Alea* (Caillois, 1957), but not too much, because it will prevent to recognize the technical merits of the players. This

tension is an important part of play and a driving force for the players (Huizinga, 1971). It can lead people to a "flow state", "the holistic experience that people feel when they act with total involvement" (Csikszentmihályi, 1975; Csikszentmihályi, 1996), which is positively correlated with optimal performance in the fields of artistic and scientific creativity (Perry, 1999; Sawyer, 1992).

Considering the impact of serious gaming on ideation process, the time pressure and the competition and the use of randomness elements show great potential, but must be defined carefully. Having an excessive time to perform a task can result, for instance, in a lower rate of production (Parkinson, 1957). Research on the effects of time pressure on creativity produced a positive effect on productivity without negatively impacting the creativity of their output (Sartawi, 2005). Similarly, competition can boost the creativity process, but the sessions should be strictly designed in order not to interfere its primary objective, expressed in terms of creative output (Shalley & Oldham, 1997). Finally, even knowing that adding randomness could reduce the creative flexibility in certain case (Svensson, Norlander, & Archer, 2002), this technique has capacity to break conventional pattern (Kultima et al., 2008) and reach originality.

This is why, balancing between structural aspects, such as features, game rules, and creative aspects, such as divergence and convergence, demands a profound understanding in both domains.

RESEARCH QUESTION AND HYPOTHESIS

In this study, we want to explore two research tracks involving technological representations. The first investigates the effect of the TechCards in a creativity session. The second examines the opportunity to turn a typical creativity session into a gaming experience with the TechCards.

Based on previous literature and our previous study, we formulated four hypotheses about the impact of these parameters on the design process. First, we suppose that an abstract technology representation in cards will improve creativity, and especially fluency and adaptation. Indeed, thanks to a fair usability and comprehensibility, the TechCards will

facilitate the first contact with technology and stimulate communication and collaboration in the creativity session, leading to ideas that are more appropriate in an industrial context. Secondary, we expect that the game experience will increase the motivation among the participants of the gaming session and will stimulate the design team to imagine more disruptive concepts and scenarios with the technology.

On the basis of the aforementioned arguments, we propose the following hypothesis (Hs):

- H1: Participants who used the TechCards will score higher on measure of fluidity than participants who did not use the TechCards.
- H2: Participants who used the TechCards will score higher on measure of adaptation than participants who did not use the TechCards.
- H3: Participant who played the game will score higher on measure of creative performance than participants who did not play the game.
- H4: Participant who played the game will score higher on measure of intrinsic motivation than participants who did not play the game.

METHOD

PARTICIPANTS

Forty-six students were enrolled in a design school from France. Participants worked in a room, in four-person groups, with a total of 12 groups participating in the experiment. On arrival, participants were randomly assigned to one of three conditions: TechCards session, Game based TechCards session and simple creativity session (Control condition).

PROCEDURE

General procedure

Participants were given standardized instruction that explained the task and established the experimental conditions. A common creative task, usual in our research center, was used: all participants in the study were told to enumerate creative use-cases for a specific set of technology (which representing the variety and the heterogeneity of the technologies developed in our company). Before the start, four rules were given:

- "We need as much ideas as possible. More ideas lead to a greater probability of finding a creative one."
- "All ideas are welcome, even the craziest."
- "Ideas proposed by someone may be combined or improved by someone else."
- "Never criticize the ideas of others! An assessment phase will come later."

Groups were given 25 minutes to work on the task. During this time, specific instructions according to the condition were given as discussed below. After 25 minutes, participants completed a 23-item questionnaire and were debriefed.

TechCards Session

In the TechCards condition, a set of six cards were presented. Participants were told to create a maximum of creative use-cases starting from cards. For example, a TechCard outside the set was presented and a use-case was given. Finally, participants were told to write their ideas on their personal post-it stack and present it to the group.

TechCards Game Session

In the TechCards game condition, the instruction was the same as the one presented before, plus some additional rules. First, each participant was told that the session had the form of a game and each group competed with the other groups: the group with the biggest number of original and relevant ideas wins. Secondly, the session was divided in 4 rounds of 5 minutes. In each round, each participant picked randomly a card and had to generate a maximum of use-case ideas in relation with the card in 5 minutes. Between each round, all participants had to present their ideas to the group.

Control Session

In the control condition, the instruction was approximately the same as the TechCards condition, except that the six technologies were reduced to a sentence and listed on a sheet of paper. This condition represents the old real condition of use-case generation in our company before the TechCards invention.

MEASURES

Creative performance

Four components of creativity, suggested by the creativity literature (Amabile, 1983; Torrance, 1962) were used in this research: fluency, adaptation, originality and overall creativity.

Fluency refers to the total number of new use-cases generated for the six technologies. Two raters, unaware of the experimental conditions, counted the total number of non-repetitious use-cases across all six technologies for each participant. The raters were in 100% agreement in regard to the total number of new use-cases by each participant. Then, this number was used as a measure of fluency in the current study.

Adaptation refers to the extent to which the use-cases generated were practical and adapted to the context (Amabile, 1983). Use-cases were clustered by technologies and each of the six sets were assessed by an expert related to the specific technology in our company. All the experts were given the instruction "Could this technology use-case be developed in our research center?" and judged whether each of use-cases were adapted (1 = *yes*; 0 = *no*). All use-cases judged to be adapted were summed for each participant and they formed a measure for adaptation.

Originality refers to the extent to which the use-cases generated were novel and original (Amabile, 1983). Similar to the adaptation measure, use-cases were clustered and assessed by specific experts from our company. All experts were given the instruction "Is this technology use-case original?" and judged whether each of use-cases was inventive (1 = *yes*; 0 = *no*). All use-cases judged to be original were summed for each participant and formed a measure for originality.

Overall creativity refers to the extent to which the uses cases generated were adapted and original (Amabile, 1983). Thus, measure of adaptation and originality were used to judge if a use-case was creative. Therefore, all use-cases judged to be adapted and original by expert were summed for each participant and formed a measure for overall creativity.

Table 1 presents the correlations among the four measures of creativity.

Table 1 - Correlations between the four measures of creativity

Measures	Fluency	Adaptation	Originality
Adaptation	0.881 [*]		
Originality	0.634 [*]	0.640 [*]	
Overall creativity	0.566 [*]	0.679 [*]	0.909 [*]

Note. * $p < .01$

Intrinsic motivation and subjective experience

Four scales from the Intrinsic Motivation Inventory (Ryan, 1982) were used: the interest/enjoyment (7 items), the Perceived Competence (6 items), the Effort/Importance (5 items) and the Pressure/Tension (5 items) subscale. Each subscale describes various statements about the subjective experience related to the activity, such as «*This activity was fun to do*». All items were measured on a 7-Point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*Not at all true*) to 7 (*Very true*). A score for each subscale was formed by reversing some items and averaging all of them.

The *Interest/Enjoyment* subscale refers to the self reported measure of intrinsic motivation related to the activity (Ryan, 1982). *Perceived Competence* concept is theorized to be a positive predictor of both self-report and behavioral measure of intrinsic motivation whereas *Pressure/Tension* is theorized to be a negative predictor (Ryan, 1982). *Effort/Importance* is a separate variable that is relevant to some motivation question and its measure could be interesting in the context of gaming.

Reliability of these measures was determined by the coefficient *alpha* (Cronbach, 1951). Internal consistency for the four subscales was generally quite adequate, as showed: *Interest/Enjoyment* ($\alpha = .84$), the *Perceived Competence* ($\alpha = .82$), the *Effort/Importance* ($\alpha = .62$) and the *Pressure/Tension* ($\alpha = .76$). The overall scale also appears to be internally consistent with an overall coefficient alpha of .78

The correlations among the four creativity measures were as follow: *Interest/Enjoyment* and *Perceived Competence* ($r = .49$, $p < .01$), *Interest/Enjoyment*

and *Effort/importance* ($r = .54$, $p < .01$), *Perceived Competence* and *Effort/importance* ($r = .63$, $p < .01$), *Perceived Competence* and *Pressure/Tension* ($r = -.30$, $p < .05$), and *Effort/importance* and *Pressure/Tension* ($r = -.29$, $p < .05$). Correlation between *Interest/Enjoyment* and *Pressure/Tension* was not significant.

RESULTS

Creative performance

Four one-way ANOVAs were used to test the difference of creative production among the three creativity sessions. Table 2 presents results for these ANOVAs. Table 3 presents the means of the three sessions into homogeneous subsets for the four measures of creativity. Groups of means that do not show up in the same column are significantly different from each other at $p < .05$, according to the Duncan Multiple-Range Test (Duncan, 1955).

Table 2 - Analysis of variance for Creativity measures and Creativity sessions

	df	MS	F	p
Fluency	2	110.90	8.45	.001
Adaptation	2	75.56	8.41	.001
Originality	2	48.08	14.77	.000
Overall creativity	2	25.65	9.41	.000

Table 3 - Homogeneous subsets for Creativity measures and Creativity sessions

	Homogeneous subsets	
	1	2
Fluency		
Control Session	6.25	
TechCards Session		9.63
TechCards Game Session		11.44
Adaptation		
Control Session	3.88	
TechCards Session		6.50
TechCards Game Session		8.19
Originality		
Control Session	1.88	
TechCards Session	2.88	
TechCards Game Session		5.25
Overall creativity		
Control Session	1.44	
TechCards Session	2.06	
TechCards Game Session		3.88

Results show a statistically significant effect among the sessions in all the four creativity measures ($p < .01$). More specifically, comparisons among means

indicated that the two conditions with TechCards scored significantly higher than in Control Session on the measure of *Fluency* ($p < .05$) and *Adaptation* ($p < .05$); thus, hypothesis H1 and H2 are validated. In addition, mean score for *Originality* ($p < .05$) and *Overall creativity* ($p < .05$) of Game session condition are significantly higher than in two other conditions; so, H4 is validated.

Intrinsic motivation and subjective experience

Four one-way ANOVAs were used to test the difference of intrinsic motivation and subjective experience among the three creativity sessions. Table 3 presents the results for these ANOVAs. Table 4 presents the means of the three sessions into homogeneous subsets for the four subscales of the Intrinsic Motivation Inventory (IMI).

Table 4 - Analysis of variance for IMI subscales and Creativity sessions

	df	MS	F	p
Interest / Enjoyment	2	4.17	5.85	.006
Perceived Competence	2	1.30	1.31	.279
Effort / Importance	2	4.11	5.95	.005
Pressure / Tension	2	0.09	0.08	.923

Table 5 - Homogeneous subsets for IMI subscales and Creativity sessions

	Homogeneous subsets	
	1	2
<i>Interest / Enjoyment</i>		
Control Session	5,01	
TechCards Session	5,39	
TechCards Game Session		6,02
<i>Perceived Competence</i>		
Control Session	4,03	
TechCards Session	4,46	
TechCards Game Session	4,57	
<i>Effort / Importance</i>		
Control Session	4,63	
TechCards Session	4,90	
TechCards Game Session		5,61
<i>Pressure / Tension</i>		
Control Session	2,41	
TechCards Game Session	2,51	
TechCards Session	2,56	

Results show a statistically significant effect on *Interest/Enjoyment* and *Effort/Importance* ($p < .01$) among sessions. Comparisons among means indicated that mean score for *Interest / Enjoyment* and *Overall creativity* ($p < .05$) of Game session condition are significantly higher than in two other conditions; so, H3 is validated.

DISCUSSION

Results and interpretation

The experimentation showed us that in both TechCards sessions (TechCards condition and TechCards Game condition) we observed more fluency and a higher number of adapted ideas. As discussed before, the fluency could be explained by the intrinsic qualities of the cards: a fair usability and comprehensibility which facilitate the first contact with technology and stimulate communication and collaboration in the creativity session. The higher number of adapted ideas could result from the framing quality of these cards, allowing more accurate technology understanding, and thus, enabling student to focus the creative process on the right technological applicability scope.

Regarding the creative and the motivational effect of the game condition, we observed an increased motivation of participants in the gaming session compared to the other conditions (TechCards condition and Control condition). These results showed the strong impacts of the manipulated game motivational leverages (competition, randomness, unpredictability and time pressure) on the creativity session, by tuning its challenge. Furthermore, the fluency score was not negatively impacted by the game external constraints. In opposition to classical literature, sustaining that external constraints are creativity inhibitors (Shalley & Oldham, 1997), this observation proves that well balanced external rules could support creativity. Moreover, we observed that in the Game condition the creative output is significantly more original and creative. We think that the game structure, and especially the added randomness, have helped to break conventional pattern. Finally, the informal gaming atmosphere reduced the social loafing effect, conducting participants to be more engaged in the creative process and more prepared to create disruptive concepts and scenarios with the technology.

Study limitations

The study results proved a better and quicker comprehension of the technology when using TechCards. However direct observation on students' activity showed us that misunderstanding about few technologies remained. We think this could be

avoided by rethinking some TechCards text elements and images. Furthermore, this study did not permit us to understand if a low number of use-cases related to a technology were due to technology misunderstanding, to card incomprehension or to intrinsic difficulties related to the specific technology to generate ideas. The TechCards effect could probably be reduced in an industrial context where the designers already know technologies developed internally. However, this could permit to better understand and integrate new technology and maintain the technical knowledge already gained.

Concerning the game experience with the TechCards, the interpretations and the results could not be generalized to a game condition without the TechCards. Hence, the effects we observed, such as motivational effect and creativity, could be explained by three different causes: a pure game effect, a cumulative effect between TechCards and game or an interaction effect between game and TechCards. A game without the TechCards condition could help us understand the real condition causes. Because the selected game rules led participants to work individually most of the time, we do not know if it can cause interferences on the game condition effect on creativity, since we know that individual creativity leads to more creative ideas than group creativity on simple task (Brophy, 2006). Finally, we stress the fact that we do not know if the motivational effect is maintained over time and repetitive gaming sessions. This is explained by an important game characteristic: the motivation effect decreases dramatically when game stimulation, induced in part by novelty, is reduced.

Perspectives

In order to control the addition of playful elements in a better way, several future studies should take into account different types of games. We suggest exploring the individual versus collective aspects of games and the degree of complexity of the implemented rules. Another research track could be to experiment new TechCards supports, from paper support towards numerical support, in order to explore and understand new experimental aspects of this tool, find new ways to understand and interact with technology and the intermediate representations.

REFERENCES

- Alvarez, J (2007). Du Jeu vidéo au Serious Game : approches culturelle, pragmatique et formelle [From Video Game to Serious Game : cultural, pragmatic and formal approaches]. Toulouse : Université de Toulouse II (Le Mirail), Université de Toulouse III (Paul Sabatier).
- Amabile, T. (1983). *The social psychology of creativity*. New York: Springer-Verlag.
- Amabile, T. M. (1996). *Creativity in context : Update to the social psychology of creativity*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.
- Bateman, C., & Boon, R. (2005). *21st Century Game Design*. London: Charles River Media.
- Bouchard, C., Camous, R., & Aoussat, A. (2005). Nature and role of intermediate representations (IR) in the design process: case studies in car design. *International journal of vehicle design*, Vol. 38, 1-25.
- Brophy, D. R. (2006). A Comparison of Individual and Group Efforts to Creatively Solve Contrasting Types of Problems. *Creativity Research Journal*, Vol. 18, No. 3
- Buchenuau, M., & Suri, J.F. (2000). Experience prototyping. In: *Conference on Designing Interactive Systems processes, practices, methods, and techniques, DIS '00*, 424-433.
- Caillois, R. (1957). *Les jeux et les hommes* [Man, Play and Games. Gallimard.
- Conti, R., Collins, M. A., & Picariello, M. L. (2001). The impact of competition on intrinsic motivation and creativity: considering gender, gender segregation and gender role orientation. *Personality and Individual Differences*, Vol. 31, No. 8, 1273-1289.
- Cronbach, L. J. (1951). Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests. *Psychometrika*, Vol. 16, 296-334.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1975). *Beyond Boredom and Anxiety*, Jossey-Bass, San Francisco, CA.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1990). *Flow: The Psychology of Optimal Experience*. New York: Harper and Row
- Csikszentmihályi, M. (1996). *Creativity: Flow and the Psychology of Discovery and Invention*. New York: Harper Perennial
- Deci, E., & Ryan, R. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, Vol. 55, 68-78.
- Duncan, D. B. (1955). Multiple range and multiple F tests. *Biometrics*, Vol. 11, 1-42.
- Fogg, B. J. (2003). *Persuasive Technology: Using Computers to Change What We Think and Do*. San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann.
- Gee, J. (2003). *What video games have to teach us about learning and literacy*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Huizinga, J. (1938/1971). *Homo Ludens - A Study of the Play Element in Culture*. The Beacon Press
- Kultima, A., Niemelä, J., Paavilainen, J., & Saarenpää, H. (2008). Designing game idea generation games. In *Conference on Future Play 2008: Research, Play, Share, Future Play '08*, New York, NY, USA, ACM Press, 137-144.
- Mednick, S. A. (1962). The associative basis of the creative process. *Psychological review*, Vol. 69, No. 3, 220-32.
- Mer, S., Jeantet, A., & Tichkiewitch, S. (1995). Les Objets Intermédiaires de la conception : Modélisation et Communication Le communicationnel pour concevoir. In J. Caelen & K. Zreik (Eds.), *Le communicationnel pour concevoir*. Paris : Europa Productions, 21-41.
- Moggridge, B. (2006). *Designing Interactions*. Cambridge: MIT Press.

- Ocnareescu, I. C., Bouchard, C., Aoussat, A., Pain, F., & Sciamma, D. (2011). *Improvement of the industrial design process by the creation and usage of intermediate representations of technology, 'TechCards'*. Manuscript submitted for publication.
- Oerter, R. (1999). *Psychologie des Spiels. Ein handlungstheoretischer Ansatz* [The psychology of play: An action-theoretical approach]. Weinheim, Germany: Beltz
- Parkinson, C. N. (1957). *Parkinson's law*. Cambridge, MA: Riverside Press.
- Perry, S. K. (1999). *Writing in flow*. Cincinnati: Writer's Digest Books.
- Ritterfeld, U., Cody, M., & Vorderer, P. (2009). *Serious Games: Mechanisms and Effects*. Mahwah, NJ: Routledge, Taylor and Francis
- Ryan, R. M. (1982). Control and information in the intrapersonal sphere: An extension of cognitive evaluation theory. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, Vol. 43, 450-461.
- Sartawi, K. (2005). The Effects of Time Pressure on Creativity. *International Business & Economic Research Proceedings*, No. 348, 1-22.
- Sawyer, K. (1992). Improvisational creativity: An analysis of jazz performance. *Creativity Research Journal*, Vol. 5, No. 3, 253-263.
- Shalley, C. E. & Oldham, G. R. (1997). Competition and Creative Performance: Effects of Competitor Presence and Visibility. *Creativity Research Journal*, Vol. 10, No. 4, 337-345.
- Svensson, N., Norlander, T., & Archer, T. (2002). Effects of Individual Performance versus Group Performance with and without de Bono Techniques for Enhancing Creativity. *The Korean Journal of Thinking & Problem Solving*, Vol. 12, No. 2, 15-34.
- Torrance, E. P. (1962). *Torrance test of Creative Thinking: Directions manual and scoring guide*. Lexington, MA: Personnel Press.
- Triantafyllakos, G., Palaigeorgiou, G., & Tsoukalas, I. A. (2011). Designing educational software with students through collaborative design games: The We!Design&Play framework. *Comput. Educ.*, Vol. 56, No. 1, 227-242.
- Vinck, D. (2009). De l'objet intermédiaire à l'objet-frontière. *Revue d'anthropologie des connaissances*, Vol. 3, No. 1, 51-72.
- Vinck, D. (1999). Les objets intermédiaires dans les réseaux de coopération scientifique : Contribution à la prise en compte des objets dans les dynamiques sociales. *Revue Française de Sociologie*, Vol. 40, No. 2, 385-414.